

A Study On Brand Loyalty Towards Lakme Products

Dr.P.Poornima ¹, Ms.M. Durga Devi ²

¹ School of applied Commerce, Assistant Professor, A.V.P
College of Arts and Science, Tirupur.

² Bachelor of Commerce with Computer Applications, School of
applied Commerce, A.V.P. College of Arts and Science, Tirupur.

Abstract – Brand loyalty plays an important role in the success of cosmetic brands in the competitive beauty market. This study focuses on analyzing consumer brand loyalty towards Lakme products. The main objective of the study is to understand the factors that influence customers to prefer Lakme products and continue purchasing them regularly. Factors such as product quality, price, brand image, product variety, availability, and advertising are considered in this study to understand consumer preferences and satisfaction. The study is based on primary data collected from consumers through questionnaires. Various analytical tools such as percentage analysis and Garrett’s ranking technique are used to interpret the data and identify the most important factors influencing brand loyalty. The findings of the study help to understand customer satisfaction levels and the reasons behind consumer loyalty towards Lakme products. It also provides useful insights for marketers to improve their strategies and strengthen customer relationships in the cosmetic industry.

Keywords: Brand Loyalty, Consumer Behavior, Customer Satisfaction, Product Quality, Brand Image, Cosmetics Industry, Lakmé Products, Marketing Strategy.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today’s highly competitive cosmetic industry, brand loyalty plays a vital role in determining the long-term success and sustainability of a company. Consumers are exposed to a wide variety of beauty and skincare products, both domestic and international, which makes their purchasing decisions more complex. In such a competitive environment, retaining customers is more important than merely attracting new ones. Brand loyalty refers to the degree to which consumers consistently prefer and repurchase a particular brand over others. It reflects customer satisfaction, trust, emotional attachment, and positive experiences associated with the brand. Brand loyalty towards Lakme products is influenced by several factors such as product quality, price, availability, brand image, advertising, celebrity endorsements, packaging, and customer satisfaction. The company has consistently introduced new product lines, including foundations, lipsticks, eyeliners, skincare creams, and sunscreens, to meet changing consumer needs. Events like the Lakme Fashion Week have further strengthened the brands image as a fashion forward and trendsetting cosmetic brand in India.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To study the demographic of the Respondents.
- To Analyze the factors influencing the Lakme products.
- To study the Brand Loyalty of Lakme products.
- To provide suggestions for improving customer retention and strengthening brand loyalty.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Research Design: Descriptive research Design Sampling Method: Convenience sampling Sample Size: 100 respondents

IV. DATA COLLECTION:

Primary Data

Questionnaire (Google Forms)

Secondary Data

Data was collected from journals, articles, books, websites and previous research studies related to brand loyalty and cosmetic products.

V. AWARE OF LAKME PRODUCT:

S. NO	PARTICULARS	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	yes	87	87
2.	No	13	13
	Total	100	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows that out of 100% of respondents, 83% of the Respondents are Yes, 17% of the Respondents are No.

The Ranks Given To The Factors Influencing Brand Loyalty

S. NO	FACTORS	1	2	3	4	5	Total	Score
1	Product Quality	3000	1500	750	400	250	5900	1
2	Price	1500	1800	1250	600	250	5400	2
3	Brand image	1125	1200	1500	800	375	5000	3
4	Product variety	1125	900	1000	1200	500	4725	4
5	Advertisement	750	600	500	1000	1125	3975	5

Interpretation:

- The first rank is given to Product Quality.
- The second rank is given to Price.
- The third rank is given to Brand Image.
- The fourth rank is given to Product Variety.
- The fifth rank is given to Advertisement.

The highest score is awarded to Product Quality, while the least score is awarded to Advertisement. This clearly shows that the respondents have given first preference to product quality in influencing brand loyalty towards Lakme.

VI. FINDINGS:

- Majority, 83% of the respondents are aware of Lakme products.
- The first rank is given to Product Quality with the highest Garrett score.
- The second rank is given to Price as it is considered an important factor influencing brand loyalty.
- The third rank is given to Brand Image, showing that respondents value the reputation of the brand.
- The fifth rank is given to Advertisement, which has the lowest Garrett score among the factors.

VII. SUGGESTIONS:

Lakme should continue to maintain high product quality, as it is the major factor influencing purchase decisions. The company can increase digital marketing and social media promotions, as many respondents became aware of Lakme through social media. Lakme can introduce more affordable product ranges to prevent customers to other brands due to price increases. The company can provide more promotional offers and discounts to encourage frequent purchases. Introducing new innovative products based on changing consumer trends can improve customer satisfaction.

VIII. CONCLUSION:

The present study titled “Brand Loyalty towards Lakme Products” was conducted to understand the level of customer loyalty, satisfaction and purchasing behaviour towards Lakme cosmetic products. The study also aimed to identify the factors influencing consumer preference and the overall perception of Lakme products among customers. From the analysis and interpretation of the collected data, Lakme has created a strong brand presence in the cosmetic market. Most of the respondents belong to the young age group, especially students and young working women, which indicates that Lakme products are highly popular among younger consumers.